

ADVANCING RESPONSIBLE CONSUMPTION: ANTICIPATING CONSUMERS' PERCEIVED VALUE TOWARDS GREEN PRODUCT PURCHASE INTENTIONS

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Abstract

Purpose- In this study, we investigate the notion of responsible consumption by examining factors that impact consumers' intentions to buy green products. Specifically, we examine how perceived value and planned behavior theory influence these intentions. By researching how customers perceive the value of green items and how their intended behavior impacts their purchase decisions, we aim to shed light on strategies for encouraging environmentally responsible consumption patterns. **Methodology-** A convenience sample method was used to obtain 311 responses from consumers of green products in the Delhi-NCR region. **Results-** The study underscores the importance of functional, emotional, and social values in shaping consumer attitudes towards purchasing green products. Furthermore, consumers' intentions to purchase green products were influenced positively by their attitude and perceived behavioral control. However, personal norms had no noticeable influence.

Keywords: Theory of Planned Behavior, Green Product Purchase Intention, India, Theory of Perceived Value.

1. INTRODUCTION

Environmentalism has represented customers' shift towards sustainable consumption over the last few decades. As consumers grow more conscious of their purchasing habits and the effects they have on the environment, they prioritize purchasing environment-friendly products (Yadav & Pathak, 2016). Increased understanding and interest in sustainable consumption will impact consumer purchasing decisions (Testa et al., 2021). Promoting green products can contribute to sustainable consumption supporting the twelfth sustainable development goal to encourage responsible consumption and production patterns. In this context, a "green product" is a "product that reduces the harm on the earth or reduces depletion of natural resources and could be recycled or conserved easily" (Nekmahmud Argon et al., 2022). Consumers with better environmental knowledge are more likely to depict higher green product purchase intention (GPPI). Few researchers found that consumers' environmental awareness influences their attitudes toward green product consumption (H.M. Kamrul Hassan et al., 2022). Additionally, consumers' positive attitude towards green products has a beneficial impact on their willingness to switch from traditional products to green products (Prakash et al., 2019). Indians are considered environmentally conscious consumers (World Economic Forum, 2017); nonetheless, their choices for green products tend to fluctuate, resulting in lower green consumerism (Sunetra Maitra Paul & Pinaki Ranjan Bhattacharyya, 2023). There is a need to identify the reasons for lower green consumption instead of being highly environment-conscious (Khare, 2023). India accounts for ten of the top 11 most polluted cities worldwide, with Delhi

retaking its position as the most polluted capital city. To help improve the environment, it is imperative to determine the causes of lower green consumption and how urgently customers must shift from conventional product consumption to green product consumption. Because there is a dearth of evidence in the literature, it is crucial to assess consumer perceptions on the use of green products to determine how valuable these products are genuinely seen by customers to better understand customer perception and attitude towards green products.

When it comes to purchasing intention, the theory of planned behavior (TPB) and perceived value theory are commonly used to investigate consumers' intentions and attitudes toward various product categories including eco-bags (H.M. Kamrul Hassan et al., 2022), organic food (Kamboj & Kishor, 2022), green food products (Woo & Kim, 2019), and energy-efficient home appliances (Lin & Dong, 2023). However, existing research has incorporated the TPB to study customers' green product purchase intention (Wang et al., 2020) and also examined the impact of perceived value on consumers' attitudes (H.M. Kamrul Hassan et al., 2022). This research focuses on evaluating Indian consumers' perceived value impacting their attitudes toward green products by using the theory of perceived value to better examine their views of green product consumption and the theory of planned behavior to analyze their willingness to shift from conventional products to green products.

This research focuses on addressing the following research questions.

- A) How does perceived value influence the attitude of Indian consumers toward green product purchase intention?
- B) Which perceived value has the most significant influence on consumers' attitude towards green product purchase intention?
- C) What is the significance of the theory of planned behavior in consumers' green product purchase intention?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theory of Planned behavior (TPB)

Ajzen (1991) asserts that a person's desire to carry out a certain conduct is strengthened by his or her favorable attitude (ATT) toward it. Customers' assessment of the consequences of consuming green products positively correlates with their inclination to use green products. Prior researchers (Zhuang et al., 2021) have discovered a striking correlation between attitude and GPPI. When Sreen et al (2018) examined the GPPI of Indian consumers, they found that attitudes had the most significant influence on GPPI. The study's conclusions suggest that fostering a positive attitude toward the use of green products will enhance consumers' interests and increase their commitment to sustainable consumption.

Furthermore, consumers will be more willing to buy green products due to a heightened level of social pressure if significant others believe that they should consume green products. Subjective norm (SN) has been shown in numerous studies on consumer behavior to be a significant antecedent of intention. Examples of these studies include purchases of organic food (Chonsiripong, 2018), environmentally conscious products (Sethi & Jain, 2020), and beauty products (Dalziel & De, 2021). The research showed a strong positive correlation between purchasing intention and subjective norms.

Past research has revealed a significant relationship between the consumer's perceived behavioral control (PBC) and green product purchase intention when it comes to the consumption of green products. When people see small impediments and consider more access to resources and possibilities, their perceived behavioral control is stronger leading to a higher intention to purchase green products. According to earlier studies, people are more likely to buy green products when they feel that they influence the relevant aspects (Zhuang et al., 2021).

The following assumptions are put out regarding the TPB model:

- H1. Attitude positively influences green product purchase intention.
- H2. Subjective norms positively influence green product purchase intention.
- H3. Perceived behavioral control positively influences green product purchase intention.

2.2 Perceived value theory

Perceived value is a significant element influencing consumers' purchase attitudes. Consumers' total evaluation of a product's usefulness, known as perceived value, is determined by how they perceive what they get and are provided. According to Sheth et al., (1991) perceived value encompasses emotional value, social value, and functional value. Green products are more environmentally friendly than conventional products. As a result, this study considered the value that consumers attributed to these products, including functional, emotional, and social value, in accordance with the conclusions of earlier research (Han et al., 2017; Sangroya & Nayak, 2017; Woo & Kim, 2019).

2.2.1 Functional value

Functional value, which is shaped by the financial and/or practical utilities that consumers can gain throughout the purchase process, is an important factor in the attitudes, perceptions, and behaviors of consumers (Sheth et al., 1991). Price, quality, convenience, and other tangible and utilitarian performances are examples of functional value (Sangroya & Nayak, 2017). Functional items are typically preferred by consumers, however high costs might create negative perceptions (Liang, 2016). When it comes to green products, higher prices might be a symbol of reliability to customers (Woo & Kim, 2019). Value for money is therefore essential for encouraging positive attitudes toward green products (Rahnama Haratbar & Rajabpour, 2017). Therefore, we hypothesize:

- H4. Functional value positively influences attitude towards green product purchase intention.

2.2.2 Emotional value

Emotional value (EV) refers to the perceived utility of a product's ability to elicit emotional responses. Emotional worth is formed from feelings or affective states (Sheth et al., 1991). Sheth et al (1991) proposed seeing the consumer experience as a system encompassing awareness, emotions, and values to understand the impact of emotions on purchasing and consumption decisions. Emotions are considered crucial in shaping consumer experiences and attitudes. Research suggests that consumers' emotions positively influence their purchase decisions for green products (Sangroya & Nayak, 2017). Woo & Kim (2019) discovered a favorable correlation

between environmental and emotional value when purchasing green products. Therefore, we hypothesize:

H5. Emotional value positively influences attitude towards green product purchase intention.

2.2.3 Social value

Social value (SV) refers to the usefulness gained from identifying with specific social groups (Sheth et al., 1991). Consumer green product decision-making is heavily influenced by social pressure (Shoukat et al., 2021). Consumers create their identity by acquiring things that reflect their social standing and social acceptance. Research suggests that customers' environmental habits are influenced by social value when purchasing green products (Woo & Kim, 2019). Caniëls et al., (2021) found that social value positively influences consumers' environmental behaviors and green consumer attitude (H.M. Kamrul Hassan et al., 2022). Therefore, we hypothesize:

H6. Social value positively influences attitude towards green product purchase intention.

Figure 1 depicts the theoretical framework proposed.

Figure 1: Proposed model

3. MATERIAL AND METHODS

a. Sample selection criteria.

Delhi-NCR of India, being the most polluted capital city which includes individuals from a variety of backgrounds and has the greatest household income in comparison to other Indian metropolises, was the subject of this study (Sadiq et al., 2021). We collected responses in 2024 between January and March. Convenience sampling was utilized to collect data from individuals aged between 18 and 58. The study was limited to participants who met the screening condition of purchasing green products from offline or online retailers within the previous six months. 390 customers were reached via Google Forms. Pre-information on the purpose of the research being conducted was provided to the respondents. A total of 328 responses were received out of which

311 responses were found usable for this investigation after being cleaned to remove outliers and missing information. Table 1 displays the profiles of the respondents.

Table 1: Demographic profile of respondents

Item	Category	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	109	35.0
	Female	202	65.0
Age (Years)	18-28	98	31.5
	29-38	78	25.0
	39-48	89	28.6
	49-58	46	14.7
	Total respondents	311	100
Education	Higher secondary level	88	28.2
	Bachelor's degree	106	34.0
	Master's degree	117	37.6

b. Measures

A self-administered survey-based questionnaire, including survey items derived from prior research, was used for the present research. To improve the questionnaire's accuracy and clarity, the conceptual elements were pre-tested by incorporating opinions from 15 research specialists with a strong focus on environmental concerns. The first section of the questionnaire collected information about demographic traits displayed in Table 1 and the second section had 21 items used for analysing the green product purchase intention with a five-point Likert scale where 1 meant strongly disagreed and 5 meant strongly agreed. Consumer's attitude, subjective norms, perceived behavioral control, and green product purchase intention were evaluated based on the statements taken from past research (Ding et al., 2017; Sun & Wang, 2019). Functional value (Suphasomboon & Vassanadumrongdee, 2022), social and emotional value (Lin & Dong, 2023) were also assessed based on statements taken from past studies.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Measurement model evaluation

SEM has become an important instrument in social sciences research. The hypotheses were investigated using the Smart PLS 4.0 software. Measurement model evaluation was done to assess the fitness of data with the hypothesized model. Measurement model evaluation is a process to assess the model's ability. Firstly, the reliability of the measurement scale was assessed and subsequently, the proposed relationships between the constructs were also analysed.

Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability were used to determine the dataset's reliability and the constructs' internal consistency respectively. Cronbach's score of more than 0.7 suggests that the measuring scales have outstanding internal consistency (Hair et al., 2019). Table II reveals that all Cronbach's alpha values were more than 0.7, showing internal consistency across all measurement constructs. The composite reliability (CR) ranges from 0.850 to 0.950, far beyond the threshold value of 0.70 (Hair et al., 2019), indicating strong process dependability. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) of the respective items ranges from 1.12 to 6.94 (Table II), which

is less than the stated cutoff value of 10, indicating that the structural model is not multicollinear (Jeng, 2023). As a result, each notion is statistically unique.

Construct validity is the degree to which a measuring scale accurately reflects the constructs under study, and it is assessed using convergent and discriminant validity. The relationship between two or more test findings aiming to explore the same variable is known as convergent validity. Constructs' Average Variance Extracted (AVE) is a commonly used method for examining measuring scales' convergent validity. Table II shows that the AVE values of respective latent variables exceed the 0.5 threshold value, indicating significant convergent validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

The degree to which items differentiate between constructs is known as discriminant validity. Table III shows discriminant validity using the HTMT criterion and the Fornell-Larcker criterion. For each latent variable, the root square of the AVE values must be higher than the correlation coefficient between that variable and all other respective variables. According to Fornell & Larcker (1981), a trustworthy construct must be above the threshold value of 0.50. All the diagonal values are above the threshold value, indicating acceptable discriminant validity. Furthermore, all the HTMT ratios are smaller than 0.90. Thus, the latent variable has a high discriminant validity (Henseler et al., 2015).

Table II: Measurement Model Evaluation

Construct	Items	Loadings	Cronbach's alpha	Rho_A	CR	AVE	VIF
Attitude	ATT1	0.86	0.84	0.84	0.90	0.75	1.86
	ATT2	0.85					1.89
	ATT3	0.89					2.12
Subjective norm	SN1	0.92	0.90	0.90	0.94	0.83	2.96
	SN2	0.93					3.26
	SN3	0.88					2.32
Perceived Behavioral control	PBC1	0.91	0.86	0.88	0.92	0.78	2.51
	PBC2	0.91					2.33
	PBC3	0.84					1.98
Functional value	FV1	0.86	0.92	0.98	0.95	0.87	2.47
	FV2	0.96					5.47
	FV3	0.97					6.08
Emotional value	EV1	0.82	0.76	0.79	0.85	0.66	6.86
	EV2	0.83					6.94
	EV3	0.78					1.12
Social Value	SV1	0.80	0.79	0.81	0.88	0.70	2.16
	SV2	0.80					1.44
	SV3	0.91					2.67
Green Product Purchase Intention	GPPI1	0.95	0.89	0.91	0.93	0.82	6.20
	GPPI2	0.95					5.85
	GPPI3	0.82					1.77

Table III: Discriminant Validity (HTMT & FLC)

Heterotrait Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)							
	ATT	EV	FV	GPPI	PBC	SN	SV
ATT							
EV	0.58						
FV	0.56	0.66					
GPPI	0.72	0.70	0.80				
PBC	0.55	0.53	0.78	0.78			
SN	0.51	0.48	0.65	0.58	0.73		
SV	0.66	0.59	0.71	0.90	0.58	0.49	
Fornell-Lacker Criterion (FLC)							
	ATT	EV	FV	GPPI	PBC	SN	SV
ATT	0.87						
EV	0.50	0.81					
FV	0.51	0.61	0.93				
GPPI	0.63	0.64	0.73	0.91			
PBC	0.46	0.48	0.70	0.69	0.89		
SN	0.45	0.43	0.60	0.52	0.64	0.91	
SV	0.55	0.56	0.64	0.77	0.50	0.43	0.84

4.2 Structural Model Evaluation

The structural model is utilized to evaluate the hypotheses. Table III shows the path relationship results, and R^2 was used to evaluate the proposed model's sample consistency. The R^2 threshold value is 0.10, table III indicates that the variables significantly exceed the threshold value (Hair et al., 2019). Further, PLS path predictive performance was assessed using a blindfolding strategy to calculate the Q^2 value. Table III shows the findings of the path model's Q^2 values, which reveal 0.36 for ATT and 0.63 for GPPI much above the threshold value of zero (Hair et al., 2019), depicting high prediction and relevance for the path model.

Figure II: Path analysis

The proposed hypotheses were tested using a bootstrap technique with 5,000 subsamples. Figure II displays both the SEM-PLS technique results and the relationships between the model's various variables. Five hypotheses out of six proposed hypotheses were accepted based on t-value and p-value, results depicted in Table IV. While analysing the role of TPB in enhancing GPPI, attitude and perceived behavioral control of consumers significantly exert a positive impact on consumers' green product purchase intention whereas subjective norms failed to do so. Table IV depicts ATT leads to enhanced GPPI (t-value=8.91 & p-value=0.00), resulting in acceptance of H1. Further, PBC was also found to be significantly influencing GPPI (t-value=10.48 & p-value=0.00), resulting in acceptance of H3. Only the subjective norm failed to influence the green product purchase intention of consumers, rejecting the H2, based on t-value=0.93 & p-value=0.35.

Based on the proposed hypotheses further analysis evaluated the impact of perceived value on the attitude of the consumers. Consumers' functional value (H4), emotional value (H5), and social value (H6) impact were assessed based on t-value & p-value. It was found that social value influences the attitude of consumers (t-value=5.99 & p-value=0.00), followed by emotional value (t-value=3.60 & p-value=0.00), and functional value (t-value=2.89 & p-value=0.00).

Table IV: Structural Model Evaluation

HN	Hypothesized paths	std β	M	SD	t value (bootstrap)	p-value	Results
H1	ATT -> GPPI	0.39	0.38	0.04	8.91	0.00	Supported
H2	SN -> GPPI	0.05	0.05	0.05	0.93	0.35	Not supported
H3	PBC -> GPPI	0.48	0.48	0.05	10.48	0.00	Supported
H4	FV -> ATT	0.17	0.17	0.06	2.89	0.00	Supported
H5	EV -> ATT	0.22	0.23	0.06	3.60	0.00	Supported
H6	SV -> ATT	0.32	0.32	0.05	5.99	0.00	Supported
			R-square	R-square adjusted	Q² Predict		
		ATT	0.37	0.37	0.36		
		GPPI	0.60	0.59	0.63		

Note: statistical significance for the two-tailed experiment ($p < 0.05$ and $t\text{-value} > 1.960$)

5. DISCUSSION

Global demand for green products is continuously rising because of health and environmental concerns. According to earlier research, Indian customers are quite environmentally sensitive. Domestic consumption in the nation is still low despite the extraordinary awareness and huge potential in the green product industry. Thus, using an enhanced TPB, this study attempts to investigate how customer-perceived values impact customers' green purchasing attitudes toward green products. The focal point of this study was to investigate TPB's role in green product adoption by Indian consumers. The study endorsed the significant impact of attitude and perceived behavioral control in influencing green product purchase intentions. Furthermore, the perceived value of consumers in influencing attitudes was also investigated. The findings revealed a strong influence of perceived value on the green product purchase intention of Indian consumers. This emphasizes the importance of perceived value in consumers' decision-making processes.

The first research question was focused on investigating the impact of perceived value on consumer attitudes toward green product consumption. According to the findings, consumers' perceived value plays a key role in enhancing their attitude toward green product purchase intention. Social values of a product are most likely to affect consumers' attitudes towards green product purchase intention. The motivation behind a pro-environmental attitude is a desire to appear good for society. It seems that social value plays a significant role in helping customers convert pro-environmental views into a green consumerism. The findings are aligning with previous studies claiming that making a positive impression on others, shoppers who support purchasing green products feel appreciated by their peers (Caniëls et al., 2021; Rahnama Haratbar & Rajabpour, 2017). Additionally, Emotional value enhances the consumers' attitude toward green products by providing a sense of joy or comfort. The findings are consistent with earlier research where consumers felt satisfied about making a positive contribution towards the environment (Sangroya & Nayak, 2017). Further, consumers' attitude was found to be significantly influenced by their perceived functional value. Consumers hold a positive attitude that using green products regularly may improve overall health and well-being more than using conventional products and that green products are safer than traditional products (Rahnama Haratbar & Rajabpour, 2017). Adding to the findings, the research also elucidates that social value perceived by a consumer plays the most significant role in forming a favorable attitude toward green product purchase intention over emotional values and functional values perceived by consumers in the Indian context. Given that Indian consumers are typically seen as image-conscious and behave in a way that fosters a favorable reputation among their peer groups.

Further, this research was determined to evaluate the role of the theory of planned behavior in green product purchase intention. As per the results, attitude and perceived behavioral control have a positive influence on green product purchase intention in Indian consumers, while subjective norms have no influence. Perceived behavior control has the greatest influence on purchase intention because Indian consumers believe they have control over resources and have easier access to resources, lessening the perceived difficulty of consuming green products over conventional products. Consumers generally purchase products based on their attitudes.

The attitude of the Indian consumer is a significant predictor of green product purchase intention. Indian consumers were found to have a positive attitude toward green consumption, and they are willing to move from conventional products to green products to receive the benefits, believing that the consumption of green products is beneficial to their health and the environment. Furthermore, Indian consumers do not make purchases based on their surroundings solely.

Consumers recognize that the approval of others is not important in their decision to buy green products. Their friends, coworkers, and family members did not provide any positive motivation to purchase green products. According to the TPB, marketers should focus on improving customers' green attitudes and also on reducing the perceived difficulties of green consumption to increase green consumption levels among Indian consumers.

6. IMPLICATIONS

a. Theoretical Implications

The research findings provided important theoretical additions to the existing knowledge about green product purchase intention. First, by looking at consumers' green product purchase intention via a theoretical framework that integrates the theory of planned behavior with the perceived value theory. In addition, by creating a precise framework for perceived values like emotional, social, and functional values that influence consumers' attitudes, which in turn influence consumers' attitudes towards green product purchase intention, the research findings demonstrate a cause-and-effect relationship. These mutually beneficial connections in turn support our society's trend of green consumerism. Thirdly, this study demonstrated how an effective model may assist researchers in delving into and assessing earlier works as well as inventing new, practical areas of academic knowledge. The reliable data from this research will add significance to the existing body of knowledge and scholarly literature about environmentally friendly consumption and purchases.

b. Managerial Implications

The research's conclusions have important implications for management with strategic significance from a real-world standpoint. To begin with, this empirical study will assist managers in creating a strategy framework that will raise customer awareness and eventually convince them to switch from conventional products to green products. Additionally, by educating consumers regarding the advantages of green product consumption, marketing managers will be in a better position to develop, share, and distribute creative value in the dynamic marketplaces, therefore pushing the sector toward sustainability. Also, the results clarify that consumers are strongly motivated by the need to seem respectable in society and impress others with their green product usage. This research may be used by marketers to raise consumers' perceptions of green products' social value. For instance, they may use social media campaigns to promote the use of green products, as people often voice their thoughts in line with what their social networks will tolerate.

Moreover, the research's results will be beneficial to marketing managers as they will provide some insightful information about the perceptions, attitudes, and intentions of green consumers as well as the dynamics of the green product market and current trends in the green product category particularly in developing economies. Such actual knowledge is necessary for marketers to have a thorough understanding of using creative tactics to introduce the green revolution into the competitive market structure.

7. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Although this investigation yielded informative results, there are a few constraints that future researchers may want to consider. This study focused on green products in general; future research might examine how customers' perceptions affect their attitudes toward certain product categories. Additionally, the study's limited sample may have produced biased results. To analyze consumers' intentions to purchase green products, a bigger sample size may be used in future research. Lastly, because perceived values may change in various cultural and societal situations from those examined in this study, future research may examine different variables to assess the attitude and intention relationship toward the use of green products.

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